

**Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Minimal Information in $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$
for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$**

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It is well known that one may derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution in two seemingly independent ways. The first is to maximize Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ and the second is to use reaction balance: $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((1)) for $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$. The second condition is a physical one which seemingly must exist in an ideal gas. The question then becomes: How does one formally show that this condition ((1)) is only satisfied for a unique function?

In other words, given physical conditions such as ((1)), it is not clear if one really has an average information function $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ (entropy) whose maximization subject to constraints allows one to derive the distribution. For example, one might use a physical condition such as ((1)) to obtain a distribution $p(e_i)$. One may then find the inverse function of $p(e_i)$, namely $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. Next, one may integrate $\int dp F(p) = G(p)$ and $-e_i/T \int dp = -e_i/T p$. Taking $dG/dp = -e_i/T$ which has the appearance of a maximization subject to the constraint $\sum_i -e_i/T p(e_i)$. The problem with this approach, which is used sometimes in the literature (1), is that it does not write entropy as $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ with $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$, a priori. We argue that $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$ means that $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ preserves the same average moments of e_i as the constraints $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$.

We try to show here that that ((1)) implies a unique distribution $p(e_i)$ and so justifies MaxEnt, but that in the Kaniadakis case, physical considerations lead to a distribution which does not satisfy MaxEnt in the manner in which suggest MaxEnt should be constructed.

Two Approaches to Obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

It is well-known that there exist at least two standard approaches to obtaining the MB distribution. The first is the usual maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints:

Maximize $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((2))

The second is a physical approach, i.e. one using reaction balance:

$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ ((3))

Examination of ((3)) shows a certain loss of information, i.e. and (i,j) pair such that $e_i+e_j = E$ has the same product probability, but why does this imply there exists a special entropy function which when extremized subject to moment constraints yields the same distribution? We suggest that this is an important question because one cannot simply ignore the physical condition ((3)). Considering it, however, yields a distribution without any maximization process. What if ((3)) did not maximize Shannon's entropy? Would it still be valid?

Demonstrating that ((3)) Is Equivalent to a Having a Single p(ei) Solution

It seems that a main goal of maximizing an entropy (Shannon's entropy perhaps) is to obtain a unique p(ei) function. This is important because a whole family of p(ei) functions satisfy the constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((4))$$

Nature, however, does not show a whole family of p(ei) probability distributions. One needs to find a unique one, but it must be consistent with physical considerations such as ((3)) which should hold for an ideal gas (but not necessarily in other cases). This unique distribution, however, does not need to maximize an entropy of the form $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ with $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$ and the Kaniadakis distribution shows. (We consider this in more detail in a later section.)

Given that a maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints yields the MB distribution, we try to consider why a single p(ei) function should satisfy the physical constraint (for an ideal gas) ((3)). This single function solution would then justify a maximization approach.

Given ((3)), one may consider a family of functions $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which also satisfy ((3)). In other words, we assume that one does not have a unique probability distribution. Then to first order:

$$dp(e_i) p(e_j) + p(e_i) dp(e_j) = dp(e_k) p(e_l) + p(e_k) dp(e_l) \text{ for } e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((5))$$

One also has: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } dp(e_i) = 0$, but given the huge number of i's, this constraint is not very binding. ((5)) may be re-written as

$$dp(e_i)/p(e_i) + dp(e_j)/p(e_j) = dp(e_k)/p(e_k) + dp(e_l)/p(e_l) \quad ((6))$$

One has many equations of the form ((6)) and one way to satisfy them is to state that:

$$dp(e_i) \text{ is proportional to } p(e_i) \quad ((7))$$

The statement ((7)), however, is akin to stating that there is no dp(ei), i.e no change in the functional form of p(ei). It is not clear that there is another way to satisfy all of the equations of the form ((6)). As a result, one would be inclined to consider a unique solution for p(ei). This unique solution could then be the result of a maximization of information approach, but this would have to be proved.

The Idea of Maximization of Entropy

We suggest that maximization of entropy subject to average moments of e_i constraints is a very specific process. We argue that if the constraints are of the form of average moments of e_i , e.g. ((4)) which uses e_i power 0 and e_i power 1, then this is a statistical description of a physical system. If one tries to consolidate information (and possibly interaction conditions) into a single statistical average:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) \quad ((8))$$

then given that $F(p(e_i))$ is ultimately a function of e_i , it should preserve the average e_i moment information i.e..

$$F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b \quad ((9))$$

((9)) follows from the form ((8)) (an average form), otherwise one cannot impose ((9)). The two go together. We suggest that in the literature (1), this is sometimes not imposed. We discuss this in the next section.

One may now try to argue that ((8)) represents minimum information and extremize it subject to the constraints. We have shown in previous notes that this leads to the MB and Tsallis solutions for:

$$p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{i.e. } F = \ln(p) \text{ is a solution, but for}$$

$$p(e_i)^q dF/dp = \text{constant}, \quad F = a_1 + a_2 p(e_i)^{1-q} \text{ is also a solution} \quad ((10))$$

We note that in the second case, one would use $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ as the constraint instead of $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$.

As a result, in the MB case, a physical condition ((3)) is equivalent to the notion of a single solution with minimal information. We argue, however, that this is not always the case.

Kaniadakis Distribution

One may try to create a Kaniadakis distribution based on physical considerations, i.e. argue that the distribution should behave as:

$$x^{1/k} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \text{ for } x \gg 1 \quad ((11))$$

For $x \ll 1$, one might argue that it mimic the MB distribution to second order:

$$p(x) = (1 + kx + k^2 x^2 / 2)^{-1/k} \quad ((12))$$

These are somewhat unusual conditions, but one might suggest that they are based on physical criteria. In such a case, the distribution is:

$$p(x) = (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx)^{1/k} \quad ((13))$$

The inverse function is: $F(p(x)) = x = \frac{1}{2k} (p^k - p^{-k}) \quad ((14))$

One may integrate: $\int dp F(p) =$ so-called entropy (p) $((15))$

Then d/dp (so -called entropy) = x $((15))$

This, however, is not a real maximization approach because it does not consider entropy as an average of $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ with $F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b$. We suggest that imposing physical conditions in order to obtain a distribution is not equivalent to maximizing entropy and that approaches such as $((15))$ (used in (1)), do not really represent minimal information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by either maximizing entropy subject to constraints or using reaction balance. We argue that reaction balance is based on the physics of an ideal gas and that one may obtain the MB distribution with no notion of maximization. We suggest that maximization implies a unique solution and try to show why this should be the case for the condition $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$. This, we argue, justifies the maximization of Shannon's entropy in the MB case. We argue that this maximization process should follow a very specific form: entropy = $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ such that $F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b$.

We show that it is possible to obtain a Kaniadakis distribution based on $e_i/T \gg 1$ and $e_i/T \ll 1$ conditions, Given this physically constructed distribution $p(x)$, one may find the inverse function $F(p) = x$. Integrating $\int dp F(p)$ yields a function which, upon taking d/dx , yields x . This gives the sense of maximization (see (1)), but does not really maximize information because this so-called entropy is not of the form $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ with $F(p(e_i)) = ae_i+b$.

References

1. Macedo-Filo, A. et al. Maximum Entropy Principle for Kaniadakis Statistics and Networks (2013)

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0375960113000984> equation ((9))